

Feasibility of implementing a trimodal prehabilitation program in adult oncology users

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Abstract: Cancer is the leading cause of global death; its treatment prolongs life but limits functionality. The combination of physical training, nutrition and psychological support can improve the functionality of post-surgical patients and reduce hospital costs. **Objective:** To evaluate the viability of a trimodal prehabilitation program in adults with indication for oncological surgeries at the Regional Hospital of Talca. **Method:** Evidence on prehabilitation was reviewed and normative bases for its design were established, structuring an intervention plan with a technical, financial and organizational study. **Results:** In cancer, surgery is essential, radiotherapy is accepted, and chemotherapy is common, with high costs and whose complications increase expenses. This is reduced with interdisciplinary strategies such as exercise, emotional and nutritional support, improving quality of life and reducing hospitalization costs, generating savings. Institutional Care Model financing is more efficient than Free Choice Model, allowing greater coverage. The financial study reveals that the project is viable, with positive Net Present Value and Internal Rate of Return higher than the discount rate. **Conclusion:** A trimodal prehabilitation program is a cost-effective strategy to improve the functionality and quality of life of patients with oncological surgeries, being clinically and financially beneficial.

Keywords: cost-effectiveness, quality, cancer, prehabilitation, health strategy.

Cancer is the leading cause of death worldwide, with nearly 10 million deaths in 2020(1), affecting patients' quality of life. Clinical management includes treatments such as radiotherapy and chemotherapy, although postoperative complications remain a problem. Trimodal prehabilitation seeks to improve patients' functional reserve through multidisciplinary interventions: physical training, nutritional adjustments, and psychological support(2,3). In Chile, the 2020 National Cancer Law(4) promotes a comprehensive approach to care. Prehabilitation can reduce hospital costs and has shown positive results in patients' functional capacity.

Prehabilitation can reduce hospital costs by decreasing hospital days and complications(5). Study of women with ovarian cancer shows prehabilitation results in annual savings of \$ 33.8 million compared to traditional care(6) and at the national level, a study at the *Hospital del Salvador* showed positive results in the functional capacity of patients with colorectal cancer who participated in a prehabilitation program(3). Although additional costs may be incurred initially, it is expected that in the long term it will improve the quality of life of patients and reduce hospital expenses.

Objective

Financial evaluation of the feasibility of a trimodal prehabilitation program for adults undergoing oncological surgeries at the Regional Hospital of Talca, analyzing its profitability and implementation.

Method

Evidence reviews to characterize demand and specific supply requirements. Subsequently, the market bases were established along with a Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Ecological and Legal (PESTEL) analysis and an External Factors Evaluation Matrix (EFE) and Internal Factors Evaluation Matrix (IFE). Then, a trimodal prehabilitation intervention plan was structured and subjected to a technical, financial and organizational study to establish the viability of the project.

Research development

Cancer is a disease of uncontrolled cell proliferation, transformed and evolving by natural selection, recognizing genetic changes in the tumor microenvironment as factors that generate aggressive cancer cells that can lead to the death of the patient(7).

This diagnosis is one of the non-communicable diseases with the highest growth in incidence and mortality. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), in 2022 there were 20 million new cases and nearly 10 million deaths. Before the age of 75, the risk of suffering from cancer is 20%, and cancer mortality projections are expected to continue to increase towards 2030(1). In 2022, lung cancer was the most diagnosed with 2.5 million cases, followed by breast cancer with 2.3 million(8). In Chile, 59 876 new cases were reported last year, the most common being prostate, colorectal and breast cancer, and overall causing 31 440 deaths, mainly from lung, gastric and colorectal cancer(8) and in the Maule Region, malignant tumors accounted for 19.9% of deaths(9,10). Globally, projections for 2050 suggest a 77% increase in new cases, reaching 35 million, especially in Central America(11).

New treatment techniques have improved outcomes and prolonged patient life spans by focusing on quality of life. Survivors face consequences that affect their well-being, such as dietary habits, mental health, and fertility issues. In 2019, 250 million years of healthy life were lost due to cancer(12). WHO has recommended implementing basic strategies for national cancer control plans, focusing on promotion, prevention, early detection, diagnosis, high-quality treatment, pain relief, palliative care, follow-up, scientific research and epidemiological surveillance.

In Chile, the "National Cancer Plan", developed by the Ministry of Health, addresses cancer as a social and health problem, focusing on rights and equity(13). It includes an Action Plan to ensure its sustainability and financing, covering nine thematic areas: promotion and prevention, services, human resources, epidemiological surveillance, social participation, research, management model, regulatory framework and financing. It proposes five strategic

lines, including primary prevention, health services and strengthening of the oncology network. Conventional treatments are surgery, radiotherapy and chemotherapy, along with newer approaches such as stem cell therapy and nanoparticles(14). Surgery is essential, while radiotherapy is commonly accepted by vulnerable patients and chemotherapy is frequently used in various malignancies, often combined with other treatments.

Cancer and its treatments represent a significant stress, especially in vulnerable individuals. Frailty is an important aspect in healthcare, as frail patients face a higher risk of complications, disease progression, and death. Frailty was defined in 2013 as a medical syndrome with multiple causes characterized by decreased strength and endurance. This syndrome is modifiable through interdisciplinary assessments and strategies such as physical exercise and nutritional support, which have been shown to improve quality of life and reduce early mortality in frail older adults.

According to the WHO, the global cost of cancer is \$1.16 trillion. In Chile, the total costs of cancer are estimated at 1 325 billion pesos, a figure adjusted to 2020. A national study estimates the direct annual costs at MM\$ 1 485 310 and the indirect costs at MM\$ 71 769 CLP(15).

Surgical complications negatively affect the quality of life of patients and increase expenditure on human, technical and economic resources(16). Currently, few surgical services systematically analyze the costs of these complications. A study of 1 850 surgical patients found a morbidity rate of 27.7%, varying between 10.7% and 71.4% depending on the complexity of the surgery, and 51.5% of patients had two or more complication events.

In another analysis of economic costs and hospital stay, in 5 822 people undergoing general and digestive surgery, 639 complications, 203 admissions to the Intensive Care Unit, 243 readmissions and 66 deaths were reported. Complications resulted in an average stay of 20.08 days compared to 5.48 days and costs of € 11 670 compared to € 3 354. An additional study evaluated the economic impact of postoperative complications in 1 200 patients undergoing major surgery, finding that those without complications had an average cost of

USD\$ 27 946, while those with grade IV complications incurred average costs five times higher, reaching USD\$ 159 345.

Surgery is the most important curative treatment for cancer, but it is associated with significant short- and long-term adverse effects. Prehabilitation is presented as an intervention aimed at improving the functional capacity of individuals, allowing them to better withstand future stressors. This strategy focuses on people with high risk factors, who have higher rates of complications and postoperative mortality, as well as decreased muscle function, fatigue, depression and poor quality of life. The literature indicates benefits of prehabilitation in patients undergoing gastroesophageal surgeries, showing improvements in physical performance, nutritional status, quality of life and reduction of postoperative complications(17).

There are positive results in prehabilitation programs for different types of cancer. A study in the United Kingdom with 85 people with breast cancer showed that a prehabilitation program is feasible and requires careful logistics from the multidisciplinary team(18). A systematic review in women with breast cancer showed that prehabilitation improves physical and mental health, especially with timely referrals, and reduces fatigue and disability(19). In a randomized clinical trial in patients with malignant gastroesophageal cancer, an improvement in perioperative functional status was observed. In addition, the Netherlands Audit Institute reported that patients undergoing lung cancer surgery have 35% complications and 2% 30-day mortality(20). A 2017 meta-analysis indicated that prehabilitation in high-risk patients undergoing lung cancer resection results in positive health changes and reduces postoperative risk and hospital stay by 5 days.

Prehabilitation seeks to improve the functional capacity of patients undergoing cancer treatment, focusing on modifiable risk factors through multimodal programs that include physical exercise, nutritional management, and psychological interventions(21). Its benefits include improvements in cardiorespiratory fitness, nutrition, neurocognitive function, reduction of postoperative complications, better response to treatments and shorter hospital stays(5). Although there is no single structure and design for prehabilitation, its success

depends on early identification of patients who may benefit, prescription of an effective program, and delivery over an appropriate period of time(22), As shown by a randomized controlled trial with 125 high-risk patients undergoing major abdominal surgery found that prehabilitation reduced complications by 51%. Trimodal prehabilitation resulted in a 10% to 16% decrease in postoperative complications, fewer days of hospitalization, and a closer return to previous functionality, which also reduced care costs. Despite including heterogeneous benefits including physical training, psychological support and nutritional adjustments to improve modifiable risk factors before surgery(17,23).

Physical exercise is a key component of trimodal prehabilitation, used to improve the functional capacity of patients undergoing cancer treatment. The Australian Society of Clinical Oncology recommends at least 150 minutes of moderate or 75 minutes of vigorous intensity aerobic exercise per week, plus two to three sessions of resistance exercise for four weeks or more before surgery. Prehabilitation exercise programs have shown positive results in physical fitness, muscle strength, and health-related quality of life.

Psychological support is essential for cancer patients and should be included in prehabilitation for surgery. Psychological morbidity has gained importance in the preoperative period, since it is common for patients diagnosed with cancer to present anxiety and depression, which can negatively impact pain perception and the response of the immune system, prolonging hospital stay and increasing the mortality rate. Studies indicate that 45- to 90-minute sessions, before and after surgery, focusing on relaxation and coping techniques, can reduce mood disorders and improve immune system activation.

Nutritional therapy is often undertreated in cancer patients. During treatment, 52.6% of patients are reported to have severe malnutrition and only 15.0% have an adequate nutritional level. This can be caused by gastrointestinal obstructions, alterations in metabolism, and effects such as anorexia, anxiety and pain. Poor nutrition is associated with a higher risk of surgical complications and lower tolerance to therapies. A study in patients with gastrointestinal cancer found that those who received nutritional support prior to surgery had significantly fewer serious complications compared to a control group, while maintaining

stable or elevated laboratory parameters, highlighting the importance of nutritional intervention in the preoperative stage.

A prehabilitation program for patients with colorectal cancer lasted 4 weeks, including exercise, nutritional and psychological support, as well as smoking cessation counseling if necessary. Physical training consisted of 1-hour sessions, 3 times a week, focusing on aerobic exercise and strength training. The results showed a significant decrease in severe complications at 30 days postoperatively, fewer admissions to intensive care, and a faster recovery of functional capacity(24). Another program for lung cancer patients included aerobic and resistance exercise, individualized nutritional care, and relaxation techniques. This group showed better outcomes in mental health, physical function, and fewer days of postoperative hospitalization(25). A systematic review indicates that, although there are no clear parameters for trimodal intervention, these programs are feasible to implement.

A 2022 study compared prehabilitation programs in Canada, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom, revealing that costs are CAD\$ 1 500 in Canada, € 1 000 - € 1 200 in the Netherlands, and £ 300 - £ 400 in the United Kingdom. These costs include diagnostics and assessments by a variety of professionals(21). In Canada, prehabilitation was conceptualized in 2007 at McGill University, showing the positive effect of combined interventions on patients' functional capacity before and after surgery. In the Netherlands, the "Fit4surgery" program was developed, encompassing exercise, nutrition, mental support, smoking cessation, and comorbidity management. This program required collaboration across multiple medical specialties and showed significant potential cost savings per patient by reducing complications by over 25%(21). In the United Kingdom, the design of prehabilitation programs involves the participation of patients and health professionals, with a focus on individual characteristics and various intervention strategies, both face-to-face and virtual, with a multidisciplinary team that addresses physical, psychological and nutritional areas.

The legal analysis assesses the viability of the program in relation to Chilean laws, ensuring compliance with health regulations to protect patients' rights, especially in

oncology(4). Intellectual property is important if innovative technologies are used. Equitable access to healthcare is a fundamental right. The market review shows that the rehabilitation programs at the Talca Regional Hospital focus on specific areas, leaving aside cancer patients, who only receive lymphedema management. A specialized prehabilitation program is proposed to improve the quality of care, given the increase in cancer in Chile.

PESTEL analysis is used to understand the macropolitical context in Chile, covering political, economic, social, technological, ecological and legal aspects.

The political party crisis following the "social outbreak" of October 2019 has polarized the political environment and increased public distrust. The National Cancer Law of 2020 has allowed the creation of strategies and funds to combat this disease, although the rotation of managers in the health system makes continuity difficult. Inflation in Chile has increased, but a decrease of close to 3% is reported, positioning the country favorably before the OECD. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth of more than 2.0% is expected for 2024. Chile faces a growing migration situation with 1 625 074 migrants, who have less access to health services. Technological advances have improved cancer detection and diagnosis, and telemedicine has facilitated access to health care. Since 2010, the Ministry of the Environment has promoted development focused on environmental protection, essential to mitigate health risks related to pollutants.

The EFE and IFE matrix focuses on external and internal factors respectively, affecting the organization, where each element is given a relevance factor and a rating, which are multiplied to obtain a total weighted rating.

The analysis of opportunities, threats, strengths, and weaknesses in the context of the National Cancer Plan reveals several key aspects. Among the opportunities, prehabilitation shows improvements in functional capacity and reduction of hospital costs. The linkage with Primary Health Care (PHC) allows for effective risk management, supported by a significant budget increase of \$ 44 823 million in 2024, and educational alliances that strengthen implementation in teaching hospitals. However, threats include the shortage of oncology

specialists outside metropolitan areas and resistance in public hospitals due to the lack of national evidence. Epidemiological projections suggest that unhealthy lifestyles contribute to an increase in cancer cases. Strengths include efficient use of time and continuous improvement in oncology care, while weaknesses encompass a complicated learning period, budget uncertainty, and the need for adherence and collaboration of treating physicians.

Given the increasing incidence of the cancer population in the Maule Region, it is crucial to innovate in strategies that strengthen the care model, improve clinical outcomes and quality of life, and reduce hospital costs. In 2023, it is estimated that of 1 162 641 inhabitants, 86.7% are affiliated with *Fondo Nacional de Salud (FONASA)*, with a national incidence of 250 cases per 100 000 inhabitants, suggesting that approximately 2 500 people could consult for cancer at the *Hospital Regional de Talca (HRT)*. For this project, a representative sample of 335 users is calculated, with a reliability of 95% and an error of 0.05. The detail of the demand for HRT is presented in Table 1.

The trimodal prehabilitation program requires a specific number of sessions to achieve significant clinical results. Kinesiotherapy interventions require 15 sessions, nutritional interventions 6 sessions, and psychological interventions 3 sessions. 44 hours of kinesiology, 22 hours of nutrition, and 22 hours of psychology are contemplated weekly, reaching a coverage of 381 people in one year. The details of the programming of activities offered are presented in Table 2.

The projection of the relationship between supply and demand is shown in Figure 1, showing the estimated demand for the program and the supply according to the values of the Institutional Care Model (ICM) and the Free Choice Model (FCM), establishing the equilibrium points and the gaps. The project proposes to work with ICM values, which would allow for the granting of nearly 200 programs for an approximate cost of CLP\$ 38 000 000, in contrast to the FCM offer that would only provide 104 programs for the same value, which will allow for greater coverage at a lower cost. It is observed that the costs of the programs, regardless of their quantity, vary by 48% between the ICM and FCM values as shown in Table 3.

The prehabilitation program requires the incorporation of certain elements for its operation, which are determined based on the projections of demand, supply and program design.

Investments include fixed assets, which are tangible assets necessary for the optimal development of the program, acquired in one go and complementing the existing service. Nominal assets are intangible assets essential to initiate the prehabilitation program. Working capital is the financial resources required to operate the program. Straight-line depreciation was used in accordance with Resolution No. 43 of 12-26-2002. Staff remuneration expenses are detailed, and the commercial scrap method is used to estimate the residual value, projecting that the total sales value will be 75% of the initial value of the assets.

The service of the Therapeutic Application Responsibility Center (TARC), which depends on the Medical Sub directorate. This service is distinguished by offering highly complex rehabilitation care, which requires a multidisciplinary, highly specialized human resource, as well as adequate infrastructure and equipment.

It is proposed that the trimodal prehabilitation program be part of the TARC Service's portfolio of benefits, and the team's professionals be under the direction, supervision and coordination of the medical head of the service.

As regards staff training, it is essential that professionals receive cross-training in specific areas to broaden their knowledge and keep abreast of innovations in the sector. In addition, it is important to make the program known to the various services and professionals to encourage their collaboration and dissemination, which is carried out as part of the program investment. The functions and costs of staff and training are presented in Table 4.

Results and Proposal for Intervention

The financial study shows Net Present Value (NPV) is a criterion that allows determining the economic viability of a project through an absolute value, considering the

value of money over time. This is established by calculating the initial investment of the project, plus the current value of future flows. This project is viable with NPV \$ 38 185 110, because, when analyzing this indicator, it adds value. Meanwhile, the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) is used in the evaluation of a project to know the profitability of an investment through a percentage value, allowing a better decision to be made. For this project, a discount rate of 10% per year is established as minimum profitability, considering the risk of the health area. This project is feasible, since the percentage of benefit is greater than the established discount rate, with an IRR of 43%.

For an oncology user to enter the program, he or she must be referred by a treating physician, meeting certain criteria such as oncological diagnosis and risk of surgical complications. An initial evaluation will be carried out by the multidisciplinary team, designing an intervention program adapted to the user's needs.

A trimodal prehabilitation program is proposed to address the growing public health problem of cancer, improving the quality of processes in HRT through a multidisciplinary and individualized approach. This innovative and low-cost project uses underused spaces, offering emotional support to users and their families. Although the social value will not be assessed at this stage, it could be considered in the future. The strategy focuses on taking advantage of the waiting time to prepare oncology users in physical and psychological aspects before starting treatments, seeking to improve clinical and economic results.

Conclusion

In recent decades, cancer has emerged as an alarming disease at a global level, with an increase in incidence, mortality and years of life lost. In the Maule region, the incidence rate exceeds the national average, which highlights the need to develop a prehabilitation program at the Talca Regional Hospital, the most complex facility in the region. This context is aggravated by the aging of the population and low rates of healthy living, which generates a greater demand for health services and high costs in care.

Prehabilitation is an emerging program with little application in the country, although international results have shown clinical, economic and social benefits. This approach offers an additional tool for oncological treatment, requiring low investment and taking advantage of existing infrastructure to ensure greater marginal productivity.

It is essential to innovate in treatments that not only improve the clinical conditions of users, but also provide social value. This project seeks to guide and support users, families and caregivers in the face of the impact of cancer.

From an economic perspective, the feasibility of implementing a trimodal prehabilitation program at the Talca Regional Hospital, aimed at users affiliated with FONASA, without copayment costs, has been demonstrated. The project, based on MAI 2024 values, required an investment of \$ 24 773 549 and projects a NPV of \$ 38 185 110 and an IRR of 43% over a 5-year horizon, considering a discount rate of 10%.

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Figure 1
Theoretical model of prehabilitation

Prepared from the publication of Carli and Zavorsky (2005). It is observed that prehabilitation increases functional capacity prior to surgery and, in addition, recovery after surgery is rapid, with greater benefit than without prehabilitation.

Table 1
Demand of oncology users of the Talca Regional Hospital

Reference	Amount	Proportions
Maule Region Population	1,162,641	100.00%
FONASA population of Maule	1,008,009	86.70%
Maule incidence*	2,520	0.25%
Representative sample (95%CI, 5%CE)	335	0.03%

*Calculated by adjusted incidence rate 250 per 100,000

Table 2
Annual schedule of activities of the prehabilitation team

Benefit	Service	Concentration	Performance*	Hours	Activity
Evaluation	Kinesiology	2	2.00	381	762
Session	Kinesiology	15	3.00	1,905	5,715
Consultation	Nutrition	6	2.00	1,143	2,286
Consultation	Psychology	3	1.33	1,127	1,500

*Performance per 60-minute chronological hour

Table 3

FCM and ICM values of prehabilitation program

Demand	FCM Value \$*	ICM Value \$*	Difference \$*	Variation %
1	366,070	189,080	176,990	
50	18,303,500	9,454,000	8,849,500	
150	54,910,500	28,362,000	26,548,500	48.5
250	91,517,500	47,080,920	44,436,580	
381	139,472,670	72,039,480	67,433,190	

*Chilean pesos

Table 4

Cost of human resources

	T¹	T²	T³	T⁴	T⁵
Kinesiology	14,280,000	14,906,92	15,561,305	16,244,446	16,957,577
Psychology	7,140,000	7,453,446	7,780,652	8,122,223	8,478,789
Nutrition	7,140,000	7,453,446	7,780,652	8,122,223	8,478,789
Administrative	4,800,000	5,010,720	5,230,691	5,460,318	5,700,026

Note: Superscript indicates the value applied to period T of the project application.